

"TO FIND OUT THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE BUYING BEHAVIOUR ON HERBICIDE"

Gaurav Acharya¹, Mukesh Kumar Maurya², Nitin kumar Soni³

Department of Agricultural Economics,

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India.

gauravbhupsa@gmail.com

mukesh.kmaurya@shiats.edu.in

(MS Received: 07.05.2023; MS Revised:09.06.2023; MS Accepted:10.06.2023)

MS 3039

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,)

Abstract

Under the direction of Dr. Mukesh Maurya, " Study on Consumer Buying Behaviour On Herbicide (Calaris Xtra) in Ambala District of Haryana was completed. Ambala district was chosen on purpose Since sugarcane output there is at a commercial level. To choose responders a multi-stage random sampling approach was used. Naringarh and Shehzadpur blocks in the Ambala district were specifically chosen out of a total of 06 blocks based on the percentage of respondents who used herbicide when growing sugarcane. Five communities were chosen at random. 120 sugarcane farmers were questioned, and they were after wards categorised into five groups (Marginal, small, semi-medium, medium and large). 06 random villages were chosen at random to receive a certain number of responders. The data was gathered by a survey method according to planned timetable. When conclusion was drawn there where it is seen that many constraints have occurred and identify the main constraints. The constraints were also discussed with growers and suggested some suitable measures. This present study pertains to the agriculture year 2022-2023.

Key Words – Saccharum officinarum, Farmers, Syngenta India Pvt. Ltd, Agrochemicals, Calaris Xtra, Consumer Buying Behaviour.

Introduction:

Sugarcane is a most important cash crop of India. It Involves less risk and farmers are assured up to some extent about return even in adverse condition. Sugarcane provides raw material for the second largest agro-based industry after textile. The sugar industry is an instrumental in generating the sizable employment in the rural sector directly and through its ancillary units. It is estimated that about 50 million farmers and their dependents are engaged in the cultivation of sugarcane and about 0.5 million skilled and unskilled workers are engaged in sugar factories and its allied industries. The sugar industry in India has been a focal point for socio-economic development in rural areas by mobilising rural resources, generating employment and enhancing farm income.

There are 716 installed sugar factories (Co-operative-326, Private-347 & Public-43) in the country as on 31.01.2016, with sufficient crushing capacity to produce around 330 lakh MT of sugar.

Syngenta india Pvt. Ltd is a leading industry, focused on the quality of products in Agri-inputs business is a niche player in innovative agrochemicals with strong market share in herbicide. For research purpose multistage sampling method was used with personal interviews and questionnaires with farmers, after conducting research it was found that large no. of farmer purchase sugarcane agrochemicals products from cooperative because they provide credit facility. Dealers were keeping branded product for selling. Dealers as well as farmers preferred Syngenta agrochemicals on the basis of quality of the product. Almost all agrochemicals companies generated demand from farmers by introducing various schemes, price discount and field demonstration to the farmers.

Calaris Xtra (Herbicide) are popular product of Syngenta India Pvt. Ltd. Based on above analysis on market functioning and consumer's

Selection of Respondents: For the selection of cultivators from families were listed and about 10% farmers were randomly selected from each village and then farmers reclassified in to five groups.

Selection of Market : Primary and Secondary market were selected randomly for data collection. Naraingarh and Shahzadpur were selected purposively. List of major market functionaries operating in the sample market and villages will be prepare.

Analysis of Data**Marketing Cost:**

• The total cost, incurred on marketing either in cash or in kind by the producer seller and by the various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity reaches the ultimate consumer.

$$C = CF + CM_1 + CM_2 + CM_3 + \dots + CM_n$$

Where,

C = Total cost of marketing of commodity

CF = Cost paid by the producer from the time of produce leave farm till he sale it

buying behaviour, the company should appoint sales manager and for improvement of sales of Syngenta India Pvt. Ltd. in the studied area. Company should focus on cooperative stores for development of their business as well as increase more contact with farmer through their work force and management strategies.

Research Methodology:

Selection of Districts: There are 22 District in Harayana state and district name Panchkula, Ambala, Yamunanagar, Kurukshetra, Karnal, Kaithal, Jind, Fatehabad, Hisar, Sonapat, Rohtak, Bhiwani, Jhajjar, Gurgaon, Mahendranagar, Mewat, Rawari, Sirsa, Faridabad, Panipat, Charkhi Dari, Palwal. Out of these, Ambala District of Haryana was selected purposively on the basis of maximum area under Sugarcane cultivation. Ambala district comprises of four sub-division, Ambala, Ambala Cantt, Barara and Naraingarh. Naraingarh sub-division compries 1 tehsil, Naraingarh and 1 sub tehsil Shezadpur. The significant towns in this district are Ambala Sadar, Ambala Cantt and Naraingarh.

Selection of Block: There are 06 Blocks in the district. Naraingarh and Shezadpur blocks was selected purposively for the study based on the data from block offices because it occupies prestigious place in Sugarcane cultivation. Naraingarh being located 39 km from Ambala city, the district headquarters, 52 km of Chandigarh, the state capital, 144 km of Shimla, and 230 km of New Delhi. And Shezadpur being located 30 km towards East from District headquarters Ambala.

Selection of Villages: There are a total of 100 villages in Naraingarh and Shezadpur blocks. A list of all villages along with area under Sugarcane was obtained from the block office Naraingarh and Shezadpur. Then all the villages were arranged in descending order on the basis of cultivated area of Sugarcane and 5 percent villages are randomly selected for the study.

CM_i = Cost incurred by the ith middleman in the process of buying and selling the product.

Marketing Efficiency:

• It was calculated using Acharya's Modified Marketing efficiency as follows -

$$MME = \frac{FP}{MC + MM}$$

Where, MME is modified measure of marketing efficiency

FP = Price received by farmers

MC = Marketing cost

Marketing margin:

Absolute margin = P_{Ri} – (P_{pi} + C_{mi})

$$\text{Per cent Position} = \frac{100 * (R_{ij} - 0.50)}{N_j}$$

Per cent margin =

Where,

PR_i= Total value of receiptsP_{pi}= Total purchase value of good (purchase price) andC_{mi}= Cost incurred in marketing**Producer Share in Consumer Rupee:**

It is the price received by the farmer expressed as a percentage of the retail price (i.e., price paid by the consumer) **PS** = **$\frac{PF}{PR} \times 100$**

$$\text{Per cent Position} = \frac{100 * (R_{ij} - 0.50)}{N_j}$$

PR

Where, PF= Price received by the farmer

PR =Retail price (consumer price)

Garrett Ranking Method

It is used to find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcome of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of following formula:

Where,R_{ij} is the rank given to ith item by the jth individual,N_{ij} is the number of items ranked by the jth individual.**Results And Discussion****Marketing channels identified in the study area:**

1. Company - Distributer - Dealer - Customer/Farmer
Company - Distributer - Customer/Farmer

Table 1: Marketing Margin And Marketing Efficiency (Syngenta Calaris Xtra)

Particulars	Channel 1	Channel 2	Channel 3	Channel 4
P price received by producer	950	950	950	950
Marketing cost incurred by;				
Producer	950	Nil	Nil	100
Commission agent			-	-
Wholesaler			360	-
Retailer		94	94	-
Retailer (Local market)	-	-	-	-
Sub total	950	94	454	950
Marketing margin				
Commission agent			-	49
Wholesaler			150	-
Retailer		150	200	
Retailer (local market)	-	-		-
Sub total		150	350	49
Total	950	244	804	999
Price paid by consumers	1500	1400	1200	1050
Price spread		15	35	4.9
Marketing efficiency%	1.578	15.737	1.492	1.051

Marketing efficiency has been worked out and presented in this table for Calaris Xtra Syngenta product. The total marketing cost and Marketing margin involved in channel –I was Rs.950, Rs.244 in channel-II, Rs.804 in channel-III and Rs.999 in channel-IV. Since the marketing cost and marketing margin in channel –III was higher, the marketing efficiency very low for channel-III. For channel-I,

Marketing Margin/Selling Profit.

Particulars	Total cost Rs / liter	Selling price Rs/liter	Net margin Rs/liter	% selling profit
Manufacture	670	950	280	29.47
Wholesaler	1050	1200	150	12.50
Retailer	1250	1500	250	16.66

Table 2 : Producer shares in consumer rupees in Ambala district of Harayana

Name of block	Syngenta		UPL (IRIS)		Bayer (Sencar)		Dhanuka (Sempra)		Total	
	Value (In Lakh)	Market Share	Value (In Lakh)	Market Share	Value (In Lakh)	Market Share	Value (In Lakh)	Market Share	Value (In Lakh)	Market Share
Banondi	146.3	20.1	440	60.5	42.5	5.8	98	13.4	726.8	100
Husaini	124.9	28.8	240	55.4	34	7.8	33.6	7.7	432.5	100
Bibipur	46.5	37.6	60	48.6	8.5	6.8	8.4	6.8	123.4	100

Total	317.7	24.7	740	57.6	85	6.6	140	10.9	1282.7	100
--------------	-------	------	-----	------	----	-----	-----	------	--------	-----

Marketing channel of Syngenta every company has to figure out a go-to-market strategy. In simpler times the company would hire sales people to sell to distributors, wholesalers, retailers or directly to final users. All the raw material required for the herbicide preparation is imported from United Kingdom through cargos to Mumbai, India and the final products is manufactured there. Finished products and send to regional headquarters by means of roadways. Finished products

Marketing channels identified in the study area:

1. COMPANY - DISTRIBUTER - DEALER - CUSTOMER/FARMER

are delivered to distributors as per their demand who sells the product either to the dealer or to the farmer directly. By using this marketing channel, the company makes the product easily available to their consumer and also eliminates middlemen which helps the company to keep the prices low of their products. The most common marketing channels engaged in the marketing of Calaris Xtra herbicide in Ambala district are following.

2. COMPANY- DISTRIBUTER-CUSTOMER/FARMER

Channel - 1: Manufacture - Wholesaler - Retailer - Consumer

Table 3 : Cost of different marketing channels of Calaris Xtra(herbicide)

S.No.	Particulars	Rs/Litre
1.	Cost incurred by the manufacture farm	670/-
i.	Bottle filling and labelling	170/-
ii.	Packaging	20/-
iii.	Weighing charges	10/-
iv.	Transportation charges	30/-
v.	Loading and unloading charges	50/-
vi.	Subtotal sales price of producer	950/-
2.	Product price incurred by wholesaler	
i.	Transportation charges	180/-
ii.	Marketing charges	30/-
iii.	Loading and unloading charges	10/-
iv.	Weighing charges	4/-
v.	Losses and miscellaneous charges	82/-
vi.	Total marketing cost of wholesaler	306/-
3.	Sale price of wholesaler to retailer	
i.	Wholesaler margin	150/-
4.	Charges born by retailer	
i.	Transportation charges	20/-
ii.	Loading and unloading charges	5/-
iii.	Marketing charges	49/-
iv.	Box charges	5/-
v.	Weighing charges	4/-
vi.	Miscellaneous charges	11/-
vii.	Total marketing cost of retailer	94/-
A.	Sale price of retailer to consumer	1406/-
B.	Calaris Xtra (Herbicide) margin	950/-
C.	Consumers paid price	1500/-

The above table reveals that the marketing cost, marketing margin and price spread for channel II. Two intermediaries were identified through which Oberon reaches to the consumers i.e., producer, wholesaler. This is the longest channel among two identified channels. The producer sells his produce to the wholesaler and wholesaler to consumer. Average marketing cost when producers sold their produce to wholesaler was Rs. 622. Among these costs miscellaneous charges was most important which is accounted for Rs.6/liter, followed by transportation Rs15. /Liter loading and unloading cost Rs.2.5/liter followed by transportation Rs.12/liter. loading and unloading cost Rs.2.5/liter., market fee Rs.2.00Rs/liter. Sale price of the producer to commission was Rs.1162/liter.

Table 4 :Constraints restricting against marketing of Herbicide

S.No.	Issues	Garett score	Rank
1.	Loyal to other Product	82	I.
2.	High Market Competition	70	II.
3.	Prices Fluctuation in Market	63	III.
4.	Packaging Problem	58	IV.
5.	Fear of New Product	48	V.
6.	Tough Product Name	42	VI.
7.	Fake Product in Market	37	VII.
8.	Retailer Influence to Purchase other Product	30	VIII.

Table 4 reveals about the constraints restricting against marketing of HERBICIDE in which (i)Loyal to other product rank (ii)High market competition rank (iii)Prices fluctuation rank (iv)packaging

Summary And Conclusion

The study recommends that marketers of herbicides should focus on improving product quality, maintaining competitive prices, and building brand reputation to attract and retain customers. It also highlights the importance of effective distribution and communication strategies to improve the availability and awareness of the product among farmers.

In current scenario and future of HERBICIDE have bright future. Farmers totally depends on the HERBICIDE that show the increasing demand of the HERBICIDE. Farmers not waste time on the field they want easy solutions for any problem of field therefore they use HERBICIDE efficiently. Due to the use of the HERBICIDE farmers yield more crops so they not stop to use the HERBICIDE. HERBICIDE are less time taken, quick action on the target organisms and safe to use. Maximum farmers use the excess quantity of the HERBICIDE but some farmers say that excess use of HERBICIDE harmful for the field and they use the HERBICIDE only when it was very essential for the crop. According to farmer without HERBICIDE in this time crop growing in effective manner is not possible because in every stage of the plant different type's weed are attacked so HERBICIDE is important for farming purpose.

References:

1. **Dev S., B and prabaharan, v. (2017)** A survey of Herbicide application in virudhunagar district, rajapalayam taluk. International journal of current science research. 1(5): 113-115

problem rank (v)Fear of new product rank (vi)Fake product in market rank (vii)High market competition rank (viii)Tough product name rank.

2. **Shetty A. and Padmanaban,N.R.(2017)** Marketing of herbicides in coimbatore district. Madras agriculture journal. 87(1):133-137.
3. **Singh SP, Shanthini. A and Kathirvel n.(2010)** Marketing challenges in weedicide in triu[ure district, tamilnadu,india.global international research analysis. 2(9): 2277-81601
4. **Bhattacharyya,A.Barik, S.R. and ganguly, P. 2009.** New Herbicide molecules, formulation technology and uses: present sttus and future challenges. The Journal of Plant Protection Sciences 1(1) : 9-15
5. **Kraehmer, Hansjoerg.** "Innovation: changing trends in herbicide discovery." Outlooks on pest management 23.3(2012): 115-118
6. **Hance,R.J.** "The behaviour of hebricide in the soil: some recent developments. " The behaviour of herbicides in the soil : some recent developments.
7. **Manish, Kumar, and N.K.Singh.** "Factors affecting farmers buying decision for herbicide in relation to weed dynamics in paddy cropla case study."International Journal of Agricultural and Statistical Sciences 11.2 (2015): 513-521